

Comparative evaluation of instrumentation time and quality of obturation using single file system and multiple file system in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years: A split mouth randomized controlled clinical trial

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Pulpectomy is the preferred line of treatment for deep dental caries using various rotary files. There is a paucity of literature on the clinical efficacy of these pediatric rotary files in achieving good quality obturation in minimum time. **Aim:** The purpose of this study is to evaluate the instrumentation time and quality of obturation using single file system and multiple file system in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years. **Method:** Study will be conducted using two different file systems for instrumentation in the same child in two different appointments. The study will be double blinded, where by, the child and the evaluator will be unaware of the file system used. The primary molars achieved through the inclusion criteria will be randomized and also the file to be used in first appointment will be randomized through coin toss method. Group A: Single file system and Group B: Multiple file system. The quality of obturation and instrumentation time was assessed and the statistical analysis was done using statistical package for social sciences. **Results:** There is difference in the instrumentation time using Single file system and Multiple file system for pulpectomy in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years and there is no difference in the quality of obturation using Single file system and Multiple file system for pulpectomy in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years respectively. **Conclusion:** The following conclusion can be drawn from the data obtained in our study: -

- Pulpectomy is possible by using single file system as an alternative to multiple file system in children
- Routine use of multiple file system for pulpectomy procedure results in discomfort in children and operator fatigue.
- No significant difference with respect to obturation quality were observed clinically after the use of single file system and multiple file system.

Keywords: single file system, multiple file system, pulpectomy, primary teeth.

INTRODUCTION:

Pediatric endodontics is a fundamental aspect of dentistry that preserves the deciduous teeth in its functional form. The sustainment of the teeth present in primary dentition becomes utmost important till it goes through the process of physiological exfoliation as it aids in the following functions such as maintenance of the arch integrity, helping with

adequate masticatory load bearing forces, phonation, esthetics, moreover it also prevents the child from developing deleterious habit which may result in malocclusion.⁽¹⁾

The major concern in the field of paediatric dentistry is early loss of primary teeth despite various efforts available in the prevention of dental caries in children. Primary teeth are considered as the natural space

maintainers. The early loss of primary teeth leads to space loss for permanent teeth to erupt due to movement of the surrounding teeth in the empty space. The main reason for loss of primary teeth is either due to dental caries or traumatic injuries, in that dental caries serves as a main cause for loss of primary teeth⁽²⁾.

Dental caries is considered to be the most chronic disease of irreversible nature which acts on the intact areas of the tooth bringing about a direct influence on the child's normal functioning. Primary tooth decay which extends into enamel and dentin can be restored normally by means of various restorative materials. However, if there is pulpal involvement of caries associated with the primary teeth, it requires pulpal treatment.

Pulpectomy is the preferred line of treatment for preserving infected deciduous teeth with irreversible pulpitis or pulpal necrosis as it would help to retain the teeth until its physiological exfoliation while maintaining its functions. However endodontics in primary teeth is more challenging because of the anatomic complexities, dynamic alteration at the root apex, close proximity to the succedaneous tooth bud coupled along with perceived difficulties in behavioural management, making paediatric endodontics a demanding task.⁽³⁾

The primary goal of instrumentation in pulpectomy of primary teeth is the effective removal of organic debris which can be achieved through biomechanical preparation and accommodate antibacterial resorbable obturating material. Complete biomechanical preparation of the canals provides a path for irrigants and also aids in sealing the canals with biocompatible obturating material while preserving the radicular anatomy.⁽⁴⁾ Hence, biomechanical preparation of canals is the major determinant in the success of pulpectomy. Maintenance of the initial morphology of canals in the root, to conserve the healthy dentin while effectively enlarging the canal to remove its infected contents is generally recommended.

Conventionally, hand K-files and H files are used to clean and prepare the root canals of infected deciduous teeth. Despite being commonly used, hand instrumentation can result in iatrogenic errors due to the indiscriminate and aggressive cutting action of stainless-steel files⁽⁵⁾ moreover the time required for the procedure is also more. Not only meticulous cleaning and debridement of the root canal but also the time taken for the treatment holds significance in Pediatric Dentistry. With the aim of achieving a quality treatment within a short period, use of rotary instrumentation has been introduced in dentistry by Barr et al in the year 2000.

It was found to be an efficient technique resulting in a uniformly shaped, conical canals with predictable obturation⁽⁶⁾. Also its ability to reduce time in canal preparation favors its use in child patients, as shorter appointment length is suggested to enhance co-operation.^{(7) (8)} Any file system which could help in

achieving a good quality obturation in minimum time duration would serve this purpose. Multiple rotary systems are available and investigated for root canal preparation of permanent and primary teeth.⁽⁹⁾⁽¹⁰⁾ These systems are primarily designed for permanent teeth. The length and taper are limitations in using existing rotary systems in primary teeth.⁽¹¹⁾ Recently, exclusive pediatric rotary files of length 16 or 17 mm are available for use in primary teeth.

The rotary file system is sub divided further into two types, that is multiple file system and single file system.

Both of these file systems offer various advantages and disadvantages.

In multiple file system more than one files are used in sequential manner for cleaning and shaping the root canal. It helps to achieve good quality of obturation.

Whereas, In single file system only one file is used for the preparation of the root canal upto working length of the root. It helps to achieve a good quality obturation in minimum time.

There is a paucity of literature on the clinical efficacy of these pediatric rotary files in achieving good quality obturation in minimum time. Thus, this in-vivo study was designed to evaluate and compare the instrumentation time and quality of obturation using two rotary systems by making the use of two practically observable parameters i.e. instrumentation time and quality of obturation.

MATERIALS:

1. Topical anesthesia
2. Syringe and needle
3. 2% lignocaine hydrochloride
4. Mouth mask, Gloves and head cap.
5. Diagnostic set of instruments
6. Explorer
7. Rubber dam
8. Sterile Cotton
9. Spoon excavator
10. Burs
11. 1% Sodium hypochlorite
12. Normal saline
13. Stop watch
14. Barbed broaches
15. Sterile paper points
16. 17% EDTA.
17. Endodontic Files (k files 10. No., Kedo S⁺ and Pedo Flex file)
18. Stainless steel crown
19. glass ionomer cement (type 9)
20. set of restorative instruments
21. Radiographic films.

METHOD:

Selection criteria:-

Inclusion criteria:

1. Teeth with irreversible pulpitis indicated for pulpectomy

2. Cooperative behavior for dental treatment under local anesthesia (class 1 or 2 in Frankel scale)¹

3. Children of age group-4 to 8 years

• **Frankel’s Behaviour rating scale(42): For selection of patients**

Score	Scoring	Observed behaviour
1	Definitely positive	Good rapport with the dentist, interested in dental procedure, laughing and enjoying the procedure.
2	Positive	Acceptance of treatment; at times cautious, willingness to comply with the dentist, at times with reservation but patient follows the dentist’s directions cooperatively.
3	Negative	Reluctant to accept treatment; uncooperative, some evidence of negative attitude but not pronounced, i.e. sullen, withdrawn
4	Definitely negative	Refusal of treatment, crying forcefully, fearful, or any other overt evidence of extreme negativism.

Exclusion criteria:

1. molars contraindicated for pulpectomy like non restorable teeth, pulpal floor perforation, excessive mobility, more than one-third of pathologic root resorption, Tooth with calcified root canals, Tooth with developmental anomalies
2. Patients with allergies to local anesthetics or sulfites
3. Syndromic patients.
4. Uncooperative patients (class 3 or 4 in Frankel scale)¹
5. Presence of frank dentoalveolar abscess or extra-oral swelling (presence of purulence in the canals)

2. Voluntary withdrawal of patient

Sample size calculation-

Sample size:

Formula for the sample size(n)

$$n = \frac{2 (Z_{\alpha} + Z_{\beta})^2 [s]^2}{(d)^2}$$

Where:

Z_{α} is the z variate of alpha error (at 95% confidence interval) i.e. a constant with value 1.96,

Z_{β} is the z variate of beta error (for power of 80%) i.e. a constant with value 0.84

Using these value

Subject withdrawal criteria:

1. Patient does not agree to sign consent form

Design	Independent
Minimum difference(δ)	0.5
SD(σ)	0.46 ²¹
TYPE I ERROR(α)	0.05
TYPE II ERROR(β)	0.20
POWER(1- β)	0.80

$$n = \frac{2 (Z_{\alpha} + Z_{\beta})^2 [s]^2}{d^2}$$

$$= \frac{2 \times (2.8)^2 (0.46)^2}{(0.50)^2}$$

$$= \frac{3.31}{0.25}$$

$$= 13.24$$

So 13.24 in each group (in each group two tailed hypothesis) which is rounded off to 15

N=15

Considering the dropouts we will consider n = 20

There will be two groups so 20×2= 40 teeth. As it will be split mouth study total number of subject for present study will be required are 20 --Sample size for study.

Study population:

Patients of age group between 4 to 8 years visiting the out-patient Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry were selected for the study.

This study was designed as split mouth Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial.

40 primary molars were randomized of 20 children. In all patients, thorough case history, clinical examination and preoperative radiographs were taken.

These was divided into 2 groups:

- GROUP A – single file system was used for biomechanical preparation during the pulpectomy procedure.
- GROUP B – multiple file system was used for biomechanical preparation during the pulpectomy procedure.

Sample randomization and allocation concealment:

Total 40 samples were assigned randomly into 2 groups (20 each) by Simple Randomization. Allocation concealment was done with Sequentially Numbered Opaque Sealed Envelope (SNOSE) method.

Consent and Assent:

Patient's parents/guardians were explained in detail about the study procedure and Informed consent (Annexure 4) was obtained from each parent/guardian and assent (Annexure 5) was obtained from child patient before including them in the study.

Plan of the study:

- Study will be conducted using two different file systems for instrumentation in the same child in two different appointments. The study will be double blinded, whereby, the child and the evaluator will be unaware of the file system used.
- 40 primary molars of 20 children fulfilling inclusion and exclusion criteria and who have deep carious lesions indicated for pulpectomy bilaterally will be selected.
- The primary molars achieved through the inclusion criteria will be randomized and also the file to be used in first appointment will be randomized through coin toss method.
- In the first appointment one type of file will be used to perform pulpectomy on molar.
- In the second appointment after a period of one week the other file system will be used in the other selected molar
- These will be divided in two groups- Group A and Group B.

GROUP A – Single File system (Kedo S⁺ file) will be used for instrumentation and then pulpectomy procedure will be performed using manufacturer's instructions.¹

GROUP B – Multiple file system (Pedo Flex file) will be used for instrumentation and then pulpectomy procedure will be performed based on manufacturer's instructions.²³

- The parents of children will be informed regarding both the methods that will be used in the study but will not be told the intervention used in particular tooth as they will be blinded to the study.

- In all the patients thorough history and full-mouth dental examination and appropriate standardized periapical radiographs will be taken of posterior teeth with possible indication for pulpectomy
- Topical anesthetic gel will be applied with a cotton roll for one minute
- Local anesthetic solutions will be delivered using appropriate syringe with needle (1ml to 1.8ml of 2% lignocaine with 1:1,00,000 epinephrine as nerve block)
- The subjective and objective signs will be verified before continuation of treatment
- After initial removal of caries, access cavity will be made using (BR-49) round bur
- The roof of the access cavity will be removed using safe ended taper fissure bur in outward brushing motion.
- A 10no. K file (ISO) file will be introduced into the root canals to check its patency.
- Extirpation of pulp will be done using barbed broches. Followed by copious irrigation using 1% of sodium hypochlorite and normal saline.
- Following pulp chamber irrigation, insertion of no. 10 K-file in the canal will be done. Radiographic working length, determination will be done by the conventional Ingle's method and kept 1 mm short of radiographic apex.
- After rubber dam isolation, the instrumentation time will be noted from the start of instrumentation until the completion of the biomechanical preparation of canals utilizing a stopwatch with the help of an assistant.
- The timer will be started after the introduction of file into the root canal and stopped after achieving a passive path.
- 17% EDTA will be used to coat the files during instrumentation.
- Irrigation will be standardized to 1% sodium hypochlorite and 15ml normal saline.
- All the canals will be obturated in the same visit only if the canals could be dried with paper points.
- Final irrigation of the root canals, for all two groups, using 1% sodium hypochlorite will be done.
- Absorbent, sterile paper points will be utilized to dry the canals followed by obturation using Metapex (Modified disposable syringe technique).²⁴
- The tooth will be then restored with Type IX GIC.
- Postoperative radiograph will be taken for the assessment of the obturation quality using bisecting angle technique.

- Evaluation of radiographs will be done by a trained assistant who is blinded to the type of file used for the preparation.
- The timer will not be stopped during the change of files (time for change of file will be counted.)²¹
- The presence of any adverse events including infection, headache, oral/tooth pain, self-inflicted soft tissue traumas such as biting of the lip/cheek will be established by two follow-up telephone calls 24 hours and one week after the treatment.
- A preformed Stainless steel crown will be placed after a period of 7 days once the tooth becomes asymptomatic
- The presence of any adverse events including infection, headache, oral/tooth pain, self-inflicted soft tissue traumas such as biting of the lip/cheek was established by two follow-up telephone calls at 24 hours and one week after the treatment.

Methods of data collection:

Objective evaluation:

Evaluation of time.

- The instrumentation time will be noted in seconds from the start of instrumentation until the completion of the biomechanical preparation of canals using a stopwatch with the help of an assistant.
- For single file system (Kedo S⁺)
- The timer will be started after the introduction of file into the root canal and stopped after achieving a passive path⁽⁴³⁾
- For multiple file system (Pedo Flex)
- The timer will not be stopped during the change of files. (the time for file change will be counted)⁽¹⁸⁾

Scoring of the scale is as follows:

Evaluation of quality of obturation.

Radiograph:

Scoring based on Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria as: (12)

- Under-filling: All the canals were filled >2 mm short of the apex.
- Optimal filling: One or more of the canals having obturating material ending at the

radiographic apex or up to 2 mm short of the apex.

- Overfilling: Any canal showing obturating material extending beyond the radiographic apex.

Statistical Method:

Data was collected and statistically analysed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 19 software. All the data were entered into Microsoft Excel 2010. All the data was entered into Microsoft Excel 2010. Descriptive statistics for instrumentation time was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for each group.

- So, it was a qualitative data. The distribution of the data in the present study was non-normal. Hence, it was analysed using non-parametric test. Two groups (Group A: pulpectomy using single file system and Group B: pulpectomy using multiple file system) were compared for various Subjective symptoms and Objective symptoms by Unpaired 't' test. Fishers' Exact test / Chi-Square Test was used to check association between two variables. Simple/Multiple bar graph, Pie chart were used for graphical representation.
- All the data were entered into Microsoft Excel 2010. Descriptive statistics for was expressed as **mean \pm standard deviation (SD), Frequency Distribution and Percentage.** Unpaired t test was used to compare two groups
- Simple/Multiple graphs were used for graphical representation.
- All the above test 'p' value was considered statistically significant when it was <0.05. The software used was SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 19.
- All the above test 'p' value was considered statistically significant when it was <0.05.

Blinding:

- It was a double blinded study whereby, patient's parents and the evaluator were unaware of the type of file system used in a particular tooth.

FIGURES:

Fig 1:Diagnostic Armamentarium

Fig 2 Armamentarium for Isolation – Rubber dam

Fig 3: Armamentarium for Pulpectomy

Fig 4: Allocation concealment- Sequentially Numbered Opaque Sealed Envelope (SNOSE) method.

Fig 5: Armamentarium for Single file system:

Fig 6 Armamentarium for Multiple file system:

Fig 7: Bilaterally deep occlusal caries of primary mandibular second molars which required pulpectomy.

- By coin method it was decided that: 84: multiple file system.
 - 75: single file system.
- By SNOSE method it was decided to use multiple file system in 1st appointment.

Tooth under consideration: 84

Filing system used: Multiple file system:

Fig 8 (a): Preoperative pic

Fig 8(b): pre operative radiograph

Fig 8(c) Time required for the procedure.

Fig 8(d) Post operative radiographs.

Evaluation of quality of obturation based on Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria (1996) as: **Optimal**
Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria (1996) as: ⁽¹²⁾

- Under-filling: All the canals were filled >2 mm short of the apex.
- Optimal filling: One or more of the canals having obturating material ending at the radiographic apex or up to 2 mm short of the apex.
- Overfilling: Any canal showing obturating material extending beyond the radiographic apex.

Fig 7): Bilaterally deep occlusal caries of primary mandibular second molars which required pulpectomy.

Tooth under consideration: 75

Filing system used: Single file system.

Fig 9 (a): preoperative pic

Fig 9 (b): pre operative radiograph

9(c) Time required for the procedure

9(d) post operative radiographs

Evaluation of quality of obturation based on Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria as(1996) .: Optimal. Scoring based on Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria as(1996):⁽¹²⁾

- Under-filling: All the canals were filled >2 mm short of the apex.
- Optimal filling: One or more of the canals having obturating material ending at the radiographic apex or up to 2 mm short of the apex.
- Overfilling: Any canal showing obturating material extending beyond the radiographic apex.

RESULTS:

There is difference in the instrumentation time using Single file system and Multiple file system for pulpectomy in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years and there is no difference in the quality of obturation using Single file system and Multiple file system for pulpectomy in primary molars in children of age group of 4-8 years respectively.

DISCUSSION:

There has been a paradigm shift in treating infected primary teeth in children from extractions to pulpectomy, which has become an important endodontic procedure in children. This helps to save teeth, preserve the arch length and guide the eruption of underlying successors⁽⁴⁴⁾. In primary teeth, the objective of pulpectomy is to completely remove the infected tissue and seal the canals with a resorbable biocompatible material. While working with children, completing the root canal procedure in a short time and at the same time providing good quality treatment is imperative. According to the systemic review conducted by Majidi Baker et al⁽⁴⁵⁾(2024), Children treated with pulpectomy in their necrotic primary molars were found to have better OHRQoL(oral health-related quality of life) than those who had their primary molars extracted. Similarly Lavanya Govindaraju et al stated that⁽⁴⁶⁾ after five years follow-up, the survival rates of the pulpectomy teeth treated under GA and LA were 81.4% and 87.4%, respectively. These findings support the fact that primary teeth pulpectomy is a viable alternative for extraction. Root canal treatment in primary teeth is both challenging as well as time-consuming in children, eminently during the canal preparation.

A practical pulpectomy technique for the primary teeth should include the following⁽²⁶⁾.

1. Fast procedure with short treatment time and minimal number of appointments.
2. Effective debridement of the root canal without weakening the tooth structure or endangering the underlining permanent teeth.
3. Minimal procedural complications.
4. Maintaining tooth function until it is naturally exfoliated.

During cleaning and shaping the root canal system, the primary objective is to remove soft and hard bacteria-containing tissue. Proper cleaning and shaping aids the irrigant to reach the apical third of the root during irrigation process resulting in sterile root canal for obturation.⁽⁴⁷⁾ Endodontic treatment is performed using reamers, files, burs, sonic instruments, and Nickel-Titanium (Ni-Ti) rotary file systems. Canal preparation with hand file techniques is time consuming and can lead to iatrogenic errors like ledging, zipping, canal transportation and apical blockage thus adversely affecting the treatment outcome for both clinician and the patients. This results in use of rotary files for root

canal preparation during endodontic treatment which reduces above mentioned complications⁽⁴⁸⁾

The design and flexibility of Ni-Ti alloy instruments allow files to preserve the original anatomy of curved canals and reduce procedural errors especially in primary teeth^{(49),(50)}. In addition, because of the funnel-shaped canal preparation, a more predictable uniform filling can be obtained in primary teeth.

Rotary files also improve patient cooperation by shortening treatment time for cleaning canals.⁽⁵¹⁾ This factor is clinically relevant in Pediatric dentistry because it allows faster procedures with maintenance of quality and security as well as reducing patient's and professional's fatigue. Considering that rotary files are more convenient to use, their application may be more appropriate in children with short attention span⁽⁵²⁾⁽⁵³⁾. The irregular canal walls of primary molars are effectively cleaned with Ni-Ti, since the clockwise motion of the rotary files pulls pulpal tissue and dentin out of the canal as the files are engaged. Due to the conical pathway of preparation and effortless entrance of obturation paste, less overfilling occurs. Ni-Ti files do not require precurvature due to their elastic memory; they are motor activated and can prepare the root canal with high speed⁽⁵⁴⁾. The probability of root canal deformation is reduced due to its elastic memory and radial aspect that keeps the file in the centre of the root canal via wall support and inactive tips.⁽⁵⁵⁾ By using rotary files, we can avoid the use of Gates-Glidden drills or round burs to remove the dentin shelf overlying the canal orifice which might cause accidental perforation of the pulpal floor or excessive removal of inner root structure especially when treating primary molars with thinner pulpal floors.⁽⁵⁶⁾ Moreover the morphology of the primary teeth differs greatly from that of the permanent teeth as the roots of the primary teeth are short, thin, curved and have softer and less dense root dentine with undetectable root resorptions.⁽⁵⁷⁾ In addition, the morphology of the root canals is ribbon-shaped which necessitates the need for an exclusive rotary file for cleaning and shaping of the primary root canals.⁽⁵¹⁾

Negotiation and thorough instrumentation of bizarre and tortuous canals encased in roots programmed for physiological resorption are the main challenges for pulpectomy⁽⁵⁸⁾. Mechanical preparation of primary teeth utilizing Ni-Ti rotary files was first done by Barr et al. (2000).⁽⁵⁹⁾ They concluded that the use of Ni-Ti rotary files for root canal preparation in primary teeth was cost effective, faster, and resulted in consistently uniform and predictable fillings. Several investigators have reported the advantages of preparation with rotary Ni-Ti instruments over the manual method for both experienced and inexperienced operators^{(60),(61)}. Silva et al.⁽⁵⁰⁾ reported that Ni-Ti rotary preparation for extracted teeth was faster than hand preparation but the canals were not as clean

Ni-Ti rotary instruments of different designs are available. Manufacturers highlight their cleaning efficacy for root canal preparations, simple procedures, and decreased procedure times, which is especially important in children. Various designs for taper, blades, grooves, and tips have been suggested.⁽⁶²⁾ The shaft designs can be grouped according to taper into two categories: progressive or constant. It has been reported that instruments with progressive tapers can shape canals more quickly than constant taper instruments.⁽⁶³⁾ In the progressive Kedo S⁺ (Single file system) have increasing taper in the coronal direction, whereas the Pedoflex (Multiple file system) files have a constant taper. It has been claimed that the increasing taper instruments have enhanced flexibility in the middle region and at the tip, and that the constant taper instruments provide a larger taper in the important apical region but make them stiff thus leading to unpredictable separation of these instruments at times leaving a segment in the instrumented canal compromising further instrumentation and effective obturation. Attempts to remove the separated portion from the canals can lead to iatrogenic complications including additional weakening of the tooth, ledging and perforations.⁽⁶⁴⁾

According to authors who initially advocated rotary technique in primary teeth, the pulpectomy technique begins with a standard access and removal of coronal tissue.⁽⁶⁵⁾ Ni-Ti PROFILE® is chosen according to that which approximates the canal size. If the single file system is selected then a single file is used up to its radiographic working length for cleaning and shaping the root-canals. On the contrary when multiple file system is selected then the canal is cleansed and shaped with sequentially larger files (more than one) until the last file binds. The rotating file is withdrawn and cleaned of pulp tissue and dentinal debris which is combined with copious irrigation followed by obturation.

An advancement in pediatric endodontics was the introduction of the exclusive pediatric Kedo S rotary file single file system with a file length of 16mm and variable taper making it, expedite its use only in primary teeth. Initially this system consisted of U1 for primary anterior teeth, D1 for mesiobuccal and mesiolingual canals, and E1 for distal and palatal canals of primary molars. These files are unique as they have a variable taper (4-8%) and a variable tip diameter. (D1-0.25 mm)⁽⁶⁶⁾. The next generation of Kedo S² files include P1 for molars and A1 for anterior teeth. These files offer advantages such as increased flexibility, reduced dentin removal, and higher resistance to cycle fatigue due to their TiO₂ coating.⁽⁶⁷⁾ The morphology of the primary teeth differs greatly from that of the permanent teeth as the roots of the primary teeth are short, thin, curved and have softer and less dense root dentine with undetectable root resorptions. In addition, the morphology of the root canals is ribbon-shaped which

necessitates the need for an exclusive rotary file for cleaning and shaping of the primary root canals.

With all these facts considered, an exclusive pediatric rotary file, Kedo-S⁺ file system (Reeganz Dental Care Pvt. Ltd. India) was introduced. The latest fifth generation of Kedo S⁺ is a single-file system with an apical cross-section that is triangular and a coronal cross-section that is tear-shaped⁽⁶⁸⁾. It consists of two Ni-Ti files (P1 plus, A1 plus) with a variable taper and working length of 16 mm to expedite its use only in primary teeth. Files have been designed for instrumentation of molars and they have a tip diameter of 0.28 and 0.38 mm respectively. P1 plus file has 4, 5, 6, 8% tapers in different lengths enabling the file to be used only in narrower canals in primary molars namely mesiobuccal and mesiolingual. A1 plus file has 4, 6, 8% tapers in different length corresponding to be used in wider canals in primary molars namely distal canal(s), which is similar to Kedo S² only difference is that these files are heat treated which gives the high resistance to cyclic fatigue and torsional fatigue making it durable and less chances of instrument separation.⁽⁶⁹⁾ Hence it was selected for the present study. In the present study, P1 plus files were used for the canal preparation.

There is paucity of literature for a study comparing the instrumentation time and quality of obturation obtained using Kedo S⁺ and PedoFlex files in a split mouth randomized control trial, making this study novel and much needed.

A study conducted by Lavanya et al revealed that more than 50% practitioners use rotary systems for biomechanical preparation in primary teeth, under which 34% practitioners use ProTaper file system.⁽⁷⁰⁾ The goal of canal shaping is to create a tapered preparation that is continuous from the crown to the apex while preserving the path. This ability to maintain this path and minimize the size of the foramen is known as the centering ability of an endodontic instrument. The study conducted by Palak J et al⁽⁷¹⁾ evaluated the transportation and centering ability of Neoendo flex orifice enlarger and Pedoflex rotary file system using CBCT imaging, revealed better centering ability of PedoFlex rotary system however there was no significant difference,⁽⁶⁹⁾ which was similar to a study conducted by Selvakumar et al⁽⁷²⁾. Another study conducted by Rituraj K et al⁽⁷³⁾ revealed Cutting efficacy of the Pedoflex rotary files was seen to be superior to that of Kedo SH and manual K files. Pedoflex files are available as multiple file system with total three color-coded files i.e. yellow, red and blue with apical tip diameter of 0.20mm, 0.25mm and 0.30 mm respectively. The use of Pedoflex files is very common due to its 16 mm length which makes its use easy in primary teeth. Hence these files were selected for the current study.

In our study 25 children (obtained using formula) of age group from 4-8 years were selected who needed pulp therapy for primary molars bilaterally. We

selected this age group, as the deciduous molar root is completed by 4 years of age and above 8 years the resorption of the roots starts to happen, for the pulpectomy procedures. This age group can show at most cooperative behaviour. Limited literature was found among this age group hence we selected 4-8 years age group.

50 primary molars of 25 children of age group 4-8 years were selected. Inclusion criteria involved child patients who had deep carious lesions indicated for pulpectomy bilaterally on mandibular second molars, children with cooperative behaviour for dental treatment under local anaesthesia (class 1 or 2 in Frankel scale), children with no history of allergic reactions to local anaesthesia or sulfites and no medical conditions contraindicating the use of local anaesthesia containing epinephrine.

Patients with allergies to local anaesthesia or sulfites, history of significant medical conditions, any medications, presence of abscess, sinus opening and uncooperative patients were excluded from this study.

Ethical and institutional research committee approval was obtained and only children whose parental consent was obtained in written before procedure were included in present study.

In all selected 25 patients, thorough case history, clinical examination and preoperative radiographs were taken. Split-mouth study was conducted using two different filing systems in the same child in two different appointments with second appointment at least a week apart.

These children were randomly divided in two groups - Group A and Group B.

- GROUP A – Molars in which single file system was used for pulpectomy procedure.
- GROUP B- Molars in which multiple file system was used for pulpectomy procedure.
- The treatment was performed by a single operator for all of the patients. Blinding of the child/parents and the evaluator of the radiograph was done and no blinding of operator was done for the type of file system used.
- Simple Randomization method and Allocation concealment proposed through Sequentially Numbered Opaque Sealed Envelope (SNOSE) method was used to determine use of single file system or multiple file system in 1st appointment.

As per randomization, 25 molars received treatment using single file system and 25 molars received treatment using multiple file system. Both file systems were compared in the same patient, thereby requiring the same armamentarium, technique and duration. This makes the comparison between single file system and multiple file system in the same patient, in two appointments is justified and unbiased.

In both the groups after drying of the mucosal tissue at the injection site with cotton gauze, topical anaesthetic

gel (benzocaine gel 20%) was applied with the help of cotton tip and left for one minute and appropriate anaesthesia was delivered and pulpectomy procedure was carried out after rubber dam application.

Access cavity was prepared, followed by pulp extirpation. Canal patency was assessed and established using No 10 k files. Instrumentation time was noted from the start of instrumentation until the completion of the biomechanical preparation of canals utilizing a stopwatch with the help of an assistant. The timer was started after the introduction of file into the root canal and stopped after achieving a passive path. For multiple file system the timer was not stopped during the change of files.

After biomechanical preparation, obturation procedure was completed using Metapex (CH plus Iodoform) as obturation material followed by post obturation restoration using Glass Ionomer Cement type IX on the same day. Stainless-steel crown was placed once the tooth became asymptomatic for both the groups.

The instrumentation time was noted in seconds and the obturation quality was verified using Modified Coll JA. and Sadrian R. criteria with the help of a trained assistant who was blinded to the type of file used.

For objective evaluation of quality of obturation in primary teeth there is only one criterion that exists and it is the gold standard proposed by Coll and Sadrian in 1996, according to which underfilling means all the canals were filled >2 mm short of apex, optimal filling one or more canals have obturating material ending at the radiographic apex or up to 2 mm short of the apex. Overfilling: Any canal showing obturating material extending beyond the radiographic apex.

Observations were recorded and data analysis was done. All the data were entered into Microsoft Excel 2010. Descriptive statistics for was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), Frequency Distribution and Percentage.

Two groups (Group A: molars treated using single file system for pulpectomy and Group B: molars treated using single file system for pulpectomy) were compared for Various Subjective and objective symptoms by Unpaired 't' test.

Fishers' Exact test / Chi-Square Test was used to check association. Unpaired t test was used to compared two groups. Simple/Multiple bar graph, Pie chart were used for graphical representation. All the above test 'p' value was considered statistically significant when it was <0.05. The software used was SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 19.

Results of total 25(considering the drop outs) subjects who were involved in this study with minimum age of 4 years and maximum age was 8 years with mean age 5 ± 1.190 .

On Comparing the Age and gender among study group it was found that, among 25 subjects who were involved in study, 9(36%) were female and 16(64%) were male. In the present study there was no

significant difference among the groups regarding age or gender, which is accordance with studies conducted by Lavanya Govindaraju et al⁽³⁸⁾ for posterior teeth and Lavanya Govindaraju et al⁽⁴⁸⁾ for anterior teeth.

On Comparison of Time (in Sec) between two groups, the results showed that, single file system (Kedo S⁺) Group (A) required less time for instrumentation compared to Group (B). There was statistically significant difference present for distribution of subjective symptoms and two groups with $p < 0.001$. Similarly in the study, conducted by Govindaraju et al there was a significantly decreased instrumentation time ($P < 0.05$) observed with Kedo-S rotary systems compared to Protaper rotary files for canal preparation in primary anterior teeth which is similar to the previous studies conducted with various multiple file rotary systems. (Shimma et al⁽⁴⁰⁾, Rasha et al⁽³⁷⁾, Shah et al⁽⁷⁴⁾, Priyadarshani et al⁽²⁴⁾. Rosa et al. (2014)⁽⁷⁵⁾ stated that the length of the appointment had a paramount influence on the behaviour of the children. The reduced instrumentation time with the use of Kedo-S plus files will create a positive impact on the child's behaviour and co-operation to the procedure. Also, it helps in reducing the fatigue of the operator.

The quality of obturation is another key element that determines the success of pulpectomy.⁽⁷⁶⁾ In the present study Out of 25 teeth in group A, 24 teeth showed optimal quality of obturation while only 1 tooth showed underfilling and none showed over filling. Likewise, out of 25 teeth in group B, 23 teeth showed optimal quality of obturation, 2 teeth showed over filling and none showed under filling. Here no significant difference can be obtained with respect to optimal quality obturation achieved using any of the file systems that is Kedo S⁺ and PedoFlex filing systems groups with $p = 0.490$, which is not in accordance with the study conducted by Shimma et al⁽⁴⁰⁾ that Kedo S⁺ revealed a greater number of optimally filled teeth (85%) & less instrumentation time (74.75 s) compared to Pedoflex files ($p < 0.05$). The maximum optimally filled canals were observed using multiple file system compared to single file system with no significant difference. ($p > 0.05$).

This indicates that after subjective and objective evaluation, in less time quality treatment can be delivered to children using Kedo S⁺ files owing to its variable taper and cross-section which is triangular till apical 3mm providing 3-point contact and then tear drop compared to PedoFlex files.

Results by comparing the type of file used appointment wise for Group A and Group B were as follows: single file was used in 11(44%) patients in 1st appointment whereas multiple filing system was used 14(56%) times. Likewise single file was used in 14(56%) patients and multiple file system was used in 11(44%) patients in 2nd appointment. There was statistically

significant difference present for distribution of the type of file used appointment wise $p = 0.396$. This clearly states that there was no bias produced based on the type of the file used in 1st or 2nd appointment.

Comparison type of teeth between two group:

Comparison type of teeth between two groups was done by Fisher's exact Test it stated that there were eight type of teeth involved in the present study. There were 8 types of teeth involved in the present study. There were 2 cases of tooth number 54 among group A while 2 in group B, 3 cases of tooth number 55 in group A while only single was in group B, 3 cases of tooth number 64 tooth in group A while single case in group B. 3 cases of tooth number 65 among group B while no case among group A, in contrast 3 cases of tooth number 74 among group A while no case in group B. Maximum cases were found of tooth number 75 i.e 8 and 7 in group A and B respectively. Tooth number 84 there were total 4 cases one among group A and 3 among group B, tooth number 85 has shown second highest tooth involved among study with 8 cases in group B and 5 cases in group A. There was statistically insignificant difference was present for teeth distribution between two groups with $p = 0.251$, Fisher's exact value = 8.916, indicated that the type of tooth did not produce bias.

CONCLUSION:

The following conclusion can be drawn from the data obtained in our study: -

- Pulpectomy is possible by using single file system as an alternative to multiple file system in children
- Routine use of multiple file system for pulpectomy procedure results in discomfort in children and operator fatigue.
- No significant difference with respect to obturation quality were observed clinically after the use of single file system and multiple file system.

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TABLES:

This study was conducted on 25 children including 50 teeth bilaterally comprising 16 males and 9 females. Minimum age was 3 years and maximum was 7 years with mean age 5±1.190. years. (Table 1 & graph 1)

Table 1: Age Statistics among study group

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age in Years	25	4	8	5	1.190

Graph 1: Age Statistics among study group

Inference:

The minimum age (in Years) among study group (n=25) was 4 while maximum was 8 with Mean 5±1.190

Table 2: Gender Distribution among study group

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Female	9	36
Male	16	64
Total	25	100

Graph 2: Gender Distribution (%) among study group

Inference: There were total 25 Subjects in the study in which 9(36%) were female and 16(64%) were male.

Table 3: Comparison of file system used between two groups by Chi-Square Test.

Group * files used Cross tabulation					
			files used		Total
			multiple file system	single file system	
Group	1st Appointment	Count	14	11	25
		% within Group	56.0%	44.0%	100.0%
		% within files used	56.0%	44.0%	50.0%
		% of Total	28.0%	22.0%	50.0%
	2nd Appointment	Count	11	14	25
		% within Group	44.0%	56.0%	100.0%
		% within files used	44.0%	56.0%	50.0%
		% of Total	22.0%	28.0%	50.0%
Total	Count	25	25	50	
	% within Group	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	
	% within files used	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	50.0%	50.0%	100.0%	
		Chi Square Test	X² = 0.720 p value = 0.396		

Statistically Insignificant

Graph 3: Comparison of file system used between two groups

Inference:

There were 14 (56%) uses of multiple file system and 11(44%) uses of Single file system in 1st Appointment. There were 11 (44%) uses of multiple file system and 14(56%) uses of Single file system in 2nd Appointment. There was statistically insignificant difference was present between two groups for type of file uses with p value= 0.396, $X^2 = X^2 = 0.720$.

Table 4: Comparison of Time (in Sec) between two groups by Unpaired ‘t’ Test.

	Single File System		Multiple file System		Mean Difference	t Value	df	Paired t Test
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				p Value
Time (in Sec)	41.0400	6.43221	49.4400	6.15819	-.040	-4.717	48	<0.001*

Statistically significant

Graph 4: Comparison of Time (in Sec) between two groups

Inference:

The mean difference for time (in Sec.) between group A single file system (41.04± 6.43) and Group B Multiple file system (49.44± 6.158) was -0.40 which was found statistically significant with p=<0.001; t=-4.717, df=48.

Table 5: Comparison type of teeth between two groups by Fisher's exact Test.

Group * teeth no. Cross tabulation											
Group		teeth no.								Total	
		54	55	64	65	74	75	84	85		
Single File System	Count	2	3	3	0	3	8	1	5	25	
	% within Group	8.0%	12.0%	12.0%	0.0%	12.0%	32.0%	4.0%	20.0%	100.0%	
	% within teeth no.	50.0%	75.0%	75.0%	0.0%	100.0%	53.3%	25.0%	38.5%	50.0%	
	% of Total	4.0%	6.0%	6.0%	0.0%	6.0%	16.0%	2.0%	10.0%	50.0%	
	Multiple file System	Count	2	1	1	3	0	7	3	8	25
		% within Group	8.0%	4.0%	4.0%	12.0%	0.0%	28.0%	12.0%	32.0%	100.0%
		% within teeth no.	50.0%	25.0%	25.0%	100.0%	0.0%	46.7%	75.0%	61.5%	50.0%
		% of Total	4.0%	2.0%	2.0%	6.0%	0.0%	14.0%	6.0%	16.0%	50.0%
Total	Count	4	4	4	3	3	15	4	13	50	
	% within Group	8.0%	8.0%	8.0%	6.0%	6.0%	30.0%	8.0%	26.0%	100.0%	
	% within teeth no.	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total	8.0%	8.0%	8.0%	6.0%	6.0%	30.0%	8.0%	26.0%	100.0%	

Fisher's Exact Test Value= 8.916 p value= 0.251

Statistically Insignificant

Graph 5: Comparison type of teeth (Frequency) between two groups

Inference:

There were 8 types of teeth involved in the present study. There were 2 cases of tooth number 54 among group A while 2 in group B, 3 cases of tooth number 55 in group A while only single was in group B, 3 cases of tooth number 64 tooth in group A while single case in group B. 3 cases of tooth number 65 among group B while no case among group A, in contrast 3 cases of tooth number 74 among group A while no case in group B. Maximum cases were found of tooth number 75 i.e. 8 and 7 in group A and B respectively. Tooth number 84 there were total 4 cases one among group A and 3 among group B, tooth number 85 has shown second highest tooth involved among study with 8 cases in group B and 5 cases in group A.

There was statistically insignificant difference was present for teeth distribution between two groups with $p=0.251$, Fisher' exact value =8.916

Table 6 Comparison Quality of root filling between two groups by Fisher's exact Test.

Group * quality Cross tabulation				Quality			Total
				optimal	over filling	under filled	
Group	Single System File	Count		24	0	1	25
		% within Group		96.0%	0.0%	4.0%	100.0%
		% within quality		51.1%	0.0%	100.0%	50.0%
		% of Total		48.0%	0.0%	2.0%	50.0%
	Multiple System file	Count		23	2	0	25
		% within Group		92.0%	8.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within quality		48.9%	100.0%	0.0%	50.0%
		% of Total		46.0%	4.0%	0.0%	50.0%
Total	Count		47	2	1	50	
	% within Group		94.0%	4.0%	2.0%	100.0%	
	% within quality		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	% of Total		94.0%	4.0%	2.0%	100.0%	
				Fisher's Exact Test value = 2.584 p value= 0.490			

Statistically Insignificant

Graph 6: Comparison Quality of filling (Frequency) between two groups:

Inference:

Among group A, there were total 24 cases of optimal filling, 1 case of under filling and no case of over filling. Among group B, there were total 23 cases of optimal filling, 2 cases of over filling and no case of under filling. There was statistically insignificant difference was present quality of filling between two groups with $p=0.490$, Fisher' exact value =2.584.

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REFERENCES:

1. Parimala K, Singh T, Shilpi T, Barkha C. Literature review on rotary endodontics in primary teeth. *SRM J Res Dent Sci.* 2021 Jan 1;12:95.
2. Sowmiya P AS Ponnudurai Arangannal, Jeevarathan J, Vijayakumar M, AarthiJ. Rotary Instruments In Pedodontics: An Overview. *Eur J Mol Amp Clin Med.* 2020;7(2):6584–7.
3. Garcia-Godoy F. Evaluation of an iodoform paste in root canal therapy for infected primary teeth. *J Dent Child.* 1987;54:30–4.
4. Siqueira JF, Araújo MC, Garcia PF, Fraga RC, Dantas CJ. Histological evaluation of the effectiveness of five instrumentation techniques for cleaning the apical third of root canals. *J Endod.* 1997 Aug;23(8):499–502.
5. Barr ES, Kleier DJ, Barr NV. Use of nickel-titanium rotary files for root canal preparation in primary teeth. *Pediatr Dent.* 1999;21(7):453–4.
6. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian EMG. Comparison of quality of obturation and instrumentation time using hand files and two rotary file systems in primary molars: A single-blinded randomized controlled trial. *Eur J Dent.* 2017;11(3):376–9.
7. Lenchner V. The effect of appointment length on behavior of the pedodontic patient and his attitude toward dentistry. *J Dent Child.* 1966 Mar;33(2):61–74.
8. Aminabadi NA, Oskouei SG, Farahani RMZ. Dental treatment duration as an indicator of the behavior of 3-to 9-year-old pediatric patients in clinical dental settings. *J Contemp Dent Pract.* 2009 Sep 1;10(5):E025-032.
9. Azar MR, Mokhtare M. Rotary Mtwo system versus manual K-file instruments: efficacy in preparing primary and permanent molar root canals. *Indian J Dent Res Off Publ Indian Soc Dent Res.* 2011;22(2):363.
10. Musale PK, Mujawar S a. V. Evaluation of the efficacy of rotary vs. hand files in root canal preparation of primary teeth in vitro using CBCT. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent Off J Eur Acad Paediatr Dent.* 2014 Apr;15(2):113–20.
11. Knowledge and practice of rotary instrumentation in primary teeth among indian dentists: A questionnaire survey Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian E - *J Int Oral Health* [Internet]. [cited 2023 Sep 11]. Available from: <https://www.jioh.org/article.asp?issn=0976-7428;year=2017;volume=9;issue=2;spage=45;epage=48;aulast=Govindaraju>
12. Coll JA, Sadrian R. Predicting pulpectomy success and its relationship to exfoliation and succedaneous dentition. *Pediatr Dent.* 1996;18(1):57–63.
13. Silva LAB, Leonardo MR, Nelson-Filho P, Tanomaru JMG. Comparison of rotary and manual instrumentation techniques on cleaning capacity and instrumentation time in deciduous molars. *J Dent Child Chic Ill.* 2004;71(1):45–7.
14. Comparison between rotary and manual instrumentation in primary teeth - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18767460/>
15. Madan N, Rathnam A, Shigli AL, Indushekar KR. K-file vs ProFiles in cleaning capacity and instrumentation time in primary molar root canals: an in vitro study. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent.* 2011;29(1):2–6.
16. Makarem A, Ravandeh N, Ebrahimi M. Radiographic Assessment and Chair Time of Rotary Instruments in the Pulpectomy of Primary Second Molar Teeth: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial. *J Dent Res Dent Clin Dent Prospects.* 2014;8(2):84–9.
17. Jp V. Instrumentation Time Efficiency Of Rotary And Hand Instrumentation Performed On Vital And Necrotic Human Primary Teeth: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Dentistry* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2023 Oct 26];04(04). Available from: <https://www.omicsonline.org/open-access/instrumentation-time-efficiency-of-rotary-and-hand-instrumentation-performed-on-vital-and-necrotic-human-primary-teeth-a-randomized-clinical-trial-2161-1122.1000214.php?aid=24750>
18. Katge F, Chimata VK, Poojari M, Shetty S, Rusawat B. Comparison of cleaning Efficacy and Instrumentation Time between Rotary and Manual Instrumentation Techniques in Primary Teeth: An in vitro Study. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2016;9(2):124–7.
19. 4-1-19-371.pdf [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: <https://www.oraljournal.com/pdf/2018/vol4issue1/PartA/4-1-19-371.pdf>

20. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Emg S, Vishawanathaiah S. Assessment of Quality of Obturation, Instrumentation Time and Intensity of Pain with Pediatric Rotary File (Kedo-S) in Primary Anterior Teeth: A Randomized Controlled Clinical Trial. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2018;11(6):462–7.
21. Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L. Clinical comparison of Kedo-S paediatric rotary files vs manual instrumentation for root canal preparation in primary molars: a double blinded randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent Off J Eur Acad Paediatr Dent*. 2018 Aug;19(4):273–8.
22. (PDF) Impact on Quality of Life of Patients Treated by Different File Systems for Root Canal Treatment [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348314256_Impact_on_Quality_of_Life_of_Patients_Treated_by_Different_File_Systems_for_Root_Canal_Treatment
23. International Journal of Dental Science and Innovative Research (IJDSIR) [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: <https://www.ijdsir.com/issue/pagedata/1092/Comparison-of-the-quality-of-obturation-using-single-file-system-and-conventional-rotary-system-in-primary-teeth--A-randomized-controlled-study->
24. Priyadarshini P, Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L, Subramanian EMG. Clinical evaluation of instrumentation time and quality of obturation using paediatric hand and rotary file systems with conventional hand K-files for pulpectomy in primary mandibular molars: a double-blinded randomized controlled trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent Off J Eur Acad Paediatr Dent*. 2020 Dec;21(6):693–701.
25. Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L, Subramanian EMG, Priyadarshini P. Comparative Evaluation of Quality of Obturation and Its Effect on Postoperative Pain between Pediatric Hand and Rotary Files: A Double-blinded Randomized Controlled Trial. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2021;14(1):88–96.
26. Chauhan A, Saini S, Dua P, Mangla R. Rotary Endodontics in Pediatric Dentistry: Embracing the New Alternative. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2019;12(5):460–3.
27. Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L, Subramanian EMG, Priyadarshini P. Comparative Evaluation of Quality of Obturation and Its Effect on Postoperative Pain between Pediatric Hand and Rotary Files: A Double-blinded Randomized Controlled Trial. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2021;14(1):88–96.
28. Evaluation Of The Clinical Efficiency Of Rotary And Manual Files For Root Canal Instrumentation In Primary Teeth Pulpectomies: A Comparative Randomized Clinical Trial [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: <https://contemppediatrdent.org/evaluation-of-the-clinical-efficiency-of-rotary-and-manual-files-for-root-canal-instrumentation-in-primary-teeth-pulpectomies-a-comparative-randomized-clinical-trial/>
29. Panchal V, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian E. Comparison of instrumentation time and obturation quality between hand K-file, H-files, and rotary Kedo-S in root canal treatment of primary teeth: A randomized controlled trial. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent*. 2019;37(1):75–9.
30. Cecchin D, de Sousa-Neto MD, Pécora JD, Gariba-Silva R. Cutting efficiency of four different rotary nickel: Titanium instruments. *J Conserv Dent JCD*. 2011;14(2):117–9.
31. Preethy NA, Jeevanandan G, Mathew MG, Subramanian EM. Evaluation of Quality of Obturation Using Two Different Rotary Files and Hand Files in Primary Teeth: A Randomized Controlled Trial. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2021;14(4):471–4.
32. (PDF) Comparison of instrumentation time and obturation quality between hand K-file, H-files, and rotary Kedo-S in root canal treatment of primary teeth: A randomized controlled trial [Internet]. [cited 2023 Oct 26]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331344333_Comparison_of_instrumentation_time_and_obturation_quality_between_hand_K-file_H-files_and_rotary_Kedo-S_in_root_canal_treatment_of_primary_teeth_A_randomized_controlled_trial
33. Shah HS, Patil VM, Kamath AP, Mathur AA. Comparative Evaluation of Instrumentation Time, Obturation Time, and Radiographic Quality of Obturation Using Two Rotary Systems and Manual Technique for Primary Molar Pulpectomies - In vivo Study. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2021;12(1):55–62.
34. L S P, Rao L, Shetty A, Hegde M, Shetty C. Impact on Quality of Life of Patients Treated by Different File Systems for Root Canal Treatment. *J Health Allied Sci NU*. 2021 Jan 7;11.
35. Vaishali Naidu D, Sharada Reddy J, Patloth T, Suhasini K, Hema Chandrika I, Shaik H. Cone-beam Computed Tomographic Evaluation of the Quality of Obturation Using Different Pediatric Rotary File Systems in Primary Teeth. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2021;14(4):542–7.
36. Kaushik M, Masih U, Gojanur S, Singhal M, Mittal V. Comparative Evaluation of Instrumentation Time and Quality of Obturation between Different File Systems in Primary Molars: A Randomised Clinical

- Trial. *J Clin Diagn Res* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2023 Oct 26]; Available from: https://www.jcdr.net//article_fulltext.asp?issn=0973-709x&year=2022&month=April&volume=16&issue=4&page=ZC18-ZC22&id=16214
37. Mohamed RH, Abdelrahman AM, Sharaf AA. Evaluation of rotary file system (Kedo-S-Square) in root canal preparation of primary anterior teeth using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT)-in vitro study. *BMC Oral Health*. 2022 Jan 18;22(1):13.
38. Shah Nawaz S, Shahroz N, Zafar MA, Sajjad S, Pasha M, Hussain AS. Comparison of two different file systems on postoperative pain after root canal instrumentation: A randomized controlled trial. *Acta Marisiensis - Ser Medica*. 2023 Mar 1;69(1):37–44.
39. Kohli A, Chhabra J, Sharma K, Katyayan R, Bhatnagar P, Sharma A. Comparative Evaluation of Instrumentation Time and Quality of Obturation amongst Pediatric Rotary Endodontic System: An In Vivo Study. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2023;16(2):338–43.
40. Hadwa SM, Ghouraba RF, Kabbash IA, EL-Desouky SS. Assessment of clinical and radiographic efficiency of manual and pediatric rotary file systems in primary root canal preparation: a randomized controlled clinical trial. *BMC Oral Health*. 2023 Sep 23;23(1):687.
41. Rajain T, Tsomu K, Namdev R. Evaluation and Comparison of Effectiveness of Kedo-S Pediatric Rotary Files vs Manual Instrumentation for Root Canal Treatment in Primary Molars. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2023;16(1):22–9.
42. Mathewson REPRJ. *Fundamentals of Pediatric Dentistry*, 3rd Edition. Indian edition. Quintessence India; 2014.
43. B S, Gopikrishna V. *Grossman's Endodontic Practice - 13th edition*. 2014.
44. (Pinkham and Casa massimo 2005. Vol. 4.
45. Bakar M, Duane B. Has children's oral health-related quality of life improved more following necrotic primary molars pulpectomy or extraction? *Evid Based Dent*. 2024 May 29;25.
46. Songvejkasem M, Auychai P, Chankanka O, Songsiripraduboon S. Survival rate and associated factors affecting pulpectomy treatment outcome in primary teeth. *Clin Exp Dent Res*. 2021 Dec;7(6):978.
47. Jf S, Mc A, Pf G, Rc F, Cj D. Histological evaluation of the effectiveness of five instrumentation techniques for cleaning the apical third of root canals. *J Endod* [Internet]. 1997 Aug [cited 2024 Jun 19];23(8). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9587319/>
48. Moghaddam KN, Mehran M, Zadeh HF. Root Canal Cleaning Efficacy of Rotary and Hand Files Instrumentation in Primary Molars. *Iran Endod J*. 2009 Spring;4(2):53.
49. Application of Ni-Ti Files for pulpectomy in primary molars-method and short term clinical results. | Request PDF [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/225291623_Application_of_Ni-Ti_Files_for_pulpectomy_in_primary_molars-method_and_short_term_clinical_results
50. Comparison of rotary and manual instrumentation techniques on cleaning capacity and instrumentation time in deciduous molars - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15272656/>
51. S C, O C, C G, L P. Comparison between rotary and manual instrumentation in primary teeth. *J Clin Pediatr Dent* [Internet]. 2008 Summer [cited 2024 Jun 19];32(4). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18767460/>
52. George S, Anandaraj S, Issac JS, John SA, Harris A. Rotary endodontics in primary teeth – A review. *Saudi Dent J*. 2016 Jan;28(1):12.
53. Comparative study of root-canal preparation using Lightspeed and Quantec SC rotary NiTi instruments - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/14641438/>
54. Da K, G M, Jc B. An analysis of canal centering using mechanical instrumentation techniques. *J Endod* [Internet]. 1999 Jun [cited 2024 Jun 19];25(6). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10530247/>
55. Cl C, Ta S, Mr R, Ja S, Mm W, Gn G. Analysis of nickel-titanium versus stainless steel instrumentation by means of direct digital imaging. *J Endod* [Internet]. 1996 Nov [cited 2024 Jun 19];22(11). Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9198416/>
56. The ProTaper technique | Request PDF [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/227985101_The_ProTaper_technique

57. Jeevanandan G. Kedo-S Paediatric Rotary Files for Root Canal Preparation in Primary Teeth – Case Report. *J Clin Diagn Res JCDR*. 2017 Mar;11(3):ZR03.
58. Anatomical challenges, electronic working length determination and current developments in root canal preparation of primary molar teeth - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/23711096/>
59. Barr ES, Kleier DDJ. Use of nickel-titanium rotary files for root canal preparation in primary teeth.
60. In vitro comparison of NiTi rotary instruments and stainless steel hand instruments in root canal preparations of primary and permanent molar - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/17183182/>
61. Rotary endodontics in primary teeth – A review - PMC [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4688451/>
62. Progressive versus constant tapered shaft design using NiTi rotary instruments - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12702124/>
63. A comparative study of Endoflare-Hero Shaper and Mtwo NiTi instruments in the preparation of curved root canals - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/16104974/>
64. Greater Taper Versus Minimal Taper in Endodontic Instrumentation [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/greater-taper-versus-minimal-endodontic-barry-musikant>
65. Use of nickel-titanium rotary files for root canal preparation in primary teeth - PubMed [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10730297/>
66. Jeevanandan G. Kedo-S Paediatric Rotary Files for Root Canal Preparation in Primary Teeth - Case Report. *J Clin Diagn Res JCDR*. 2017 Mar;11(3):ZR03–5.
67. Rotary Files in Pediatric Dentistry: From Then Till Now [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jun 19]. Available from: <https://jsd.sbvjournals.com/abstractArticleContentBrowse/JSD/22999/JPJ/fullText>
68. Jeevanandan G, Ganesh S, Arthilakshmi. Kedo file system for root canal preparation in primary teeth. *Indian J Dent Res Off Publ Indian Soc Dent Res*. 2019;30(4):622–4.
69. Kumar DD, Jeevanandan DG. PEDIATRIC ROTARY FILES FROM KEDO-S PLUS FRACTURE INCIDENCE: A PROSPECTIVE CLINICAL STUDY. *J Pharm Negat Results*. 2023 Feb 8;3021–7.
70. Govindaraju L, Jeevanandan G, Subramanian E. Knowledge and practice of rotary instrumentation in primary teeth among indian dentists: A questionnaire survey. *J Int Oral Health*. 2017 Apr 15;9:45–8.
71. Janiani P, Ramakrishnan M. Canal transportation and centering ability of neoendo rotary files in deciduous teeth: An in vitro study using cone beam computed tomography. *J Popul Ther Clin Pharmacol*. 2023 May 13;30(10):19–23.
72. Asif A, Jeevanandan G, Govindaraju L, Vignesh R, G. Subramanian EM. Comparative Evaluation of Extrusion of Apical Debris in Primary Anterior Teeth using Two Different Rotary Systems and Hand Files: An In Vitro Study. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2019;10(3):512–6.
73. Kesri R, Pardhi N, Surana P, Ukey A, Agrawal PK, Agrawal S. Comparative Evaluation of Cutting Efficiency of Three File Systems—Kedo-SH Manual, Pedoflex Rotary, and Manual K File: An In Vitro Study. *J Pharm Bioallied Sci*. 2024 Feb;16(Suppl 1):S239–42.
74. Shah HS, Patil VM, Kamath AP, Mathur AA. Comparative Evaluation of Instrumentation Time, Obturation Time, and Radiographic Quality of Obturation Using Two Rotary Systems and Manual Technique for Primary Molar Pulpectomies – In vivo Study. *Contemp Clin Dent*. 2021;12(1):55–62.
75. (PDF) Manual and rotary instrumentation techniques for root canal preparation in primary molars [Internet]. [cited 2024 Apr 9]. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272728509_Manual_and_rotary_instrumentation_techniques_for_root_canal_preparation_in_primary_molars
76. Ranly DM, Garcia-Godoy F. Current and potential pulp therapies for primary and young permanent teeth. *J Dent*. 2000 Mar;28(3):153–61.